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Review Article

Ocular Gene Therapy: A Comprehensive Review with Special Focus on Inflammatory and Immune Responses

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been an increasing focus on researching gene therapy. The eye is a subject of high interest in the advancement of gene therapy, since it is one of the rare body organs where gene therapy has been sanctioned by the Food and Drug Administration. Nevertheless, the immune and inflammatory reactions linked to it can make the treatment ineffective or even detrimental. This is especially crucial for the eye, as it is susceptible to inflammation. The intensity of the immune and inflammatory reactions varies depending on the selection of vector and method of delivery. Additionally, the majority of preclinical and clinical research has demonstrated a relationship between the dosage of the vector and the level of humoral response and ocular inflammation. The method of delivery directly influences the level of immune and inflammatory responses. Subretinal administration leads to decreased fluid pressure in the eye and exhibits a superior reaction compared to the intravitreal method. Hence, certain research has shown that subretinal administration could result in a more significant impact. Response that causes inflammation. However, clinical trials utilizing viral vectors injected into the eye have documented numerous instances of vision impairment from intense inflammation within the eye, while delivering genes through the suprachoroidal route has been found to trigger a milder immune response than intravitreal injection. Hence, the suprachoroidal space does not have the same immune protection as the subretinal space. The following ophthalmic gene therapy are mild, and both clinical and preclinical research suggests that these can be managed using topical, localized, or systemic steroids.

INTRODUCTION

Gene therapy for the eyes is a revolutionary method used to treat different genetic and acquired

eye problems. This new approach to treatment requires inserting genetic material into eye cells in order to fix or change gene activity, providing

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potential for people suffering from disorders that were not treatable before. Due to its distinct anatomical and physiological features, the eye is an excellent candidate for gene therapy treatments. This extensive review focuses on examining the present status of ocular gene therapy, specifically highlighting the inflammatory and immune reactions linked to this form of treatment. We will explore the complex mechanisms behind these reactions, the difficulties they present for effective gene therapy, and the approaches being created to

address these challenges. There have been significant advancements in ocular gene therapy recently, leading to the FDA approval of the first gene therapy for an inherited retinal disease in 2017. Nevertheless, there are still several obstacles to overcome in implementing this new treatment method. One of the main priorities is to comprehend and control the intricate interaction between the introduced genetic material, the viral vectors for delivery, and the host immune system.

This review aims to give researchers, clinicians, and biotechnology professionals a comprehensive understanding by concentrating on the inflammatory and immune aspects of ocular gene therapy.

- The present situation of gene therapy for the eyes.
- The vectors and distribution techniques utilized.
- The immune reactions, both innate and adaptive, are triggered by gene therapy.
- to reduce undesired immune responses.
- The existing situation regarding clinical trials and therapies that have been approved.
- Future paths and upcoming tendencies in the field.

With this in-depth investigation, we hope to enhance ocular gene therapy to better help patients with severe eye conditions.

• **Background on Ocular Gene Therapy**

.1 Historical Development

The idea of gene therapy was introduced in the 1970s, but it wasn't until the late 1990s and early

2000s. It wasn't until the 2000s that ocular gene therapy started to become widely recognized. The distinctive qualities of the eye, such as its immune privilege, accessibility, and structured layout, made it a desirable focus for initial gene therapy tests.

- Important stages in the progress of eye gene therapy comprise.
- 1990: Initial gene transfer achievement to the retina in a mouse model.
- 2000: Showing sustained transgene expression in primate eye over extended period.
- 2008 saw the initiation of the initial human trial for Leber congenital amaurosis (LCA).
- 2017 saw the FDA give approval for Luxturna (voretigene neparvovec-rzyl) for the treatment of RPE65-mediated inherited retinal dystrophy.

Advantages of the Eye as a Target for Gene Therapy

The eye has many qualities that make it ideal for gene therapy uses.

- Immune privilege in the eye is maintained by the blood-retinal barrier and the lack of lymphatic

drainage, leading to a decreased immune response and the possibility of prolonged therapeutic benefits.

- **Accessibility:** The eye's outer position enables convenient entry for minor procedures, making it easier to administer gene therapy vectors.
- **Small volume:** The eye's small size means that less vector and transgene product are needed to achieve therapeutic results, leading to lower overall required dosage.
- **Separation into compartments in the eye** enables precise delivery to certain structures, reducing unwanted side effects.
- **Non-invasive monitoring** can be achieved through advanced imaging techniques like optical coherence tomography (OCT) and fundus autofluorescence, allowing for the observation of treatment effects.
- **Utilizing the untreated eye as an internal control** in clinical studies is possible due to having two eyes.

3 Common Ocular Disorders Amenable to Gene Therapy

Several inherited and acquired ocular disorders have been identified as potential targets for gene therapy. These include:

1. Inherited retinal diseases:
 - a. Leber congenital amaurosis (LCA)
 - b. Retinitis pigmentosa (RP)
 - c. Choroideremia
 - d. Achromatopsia
 - e. X-linked retinoschisis
2. Age-related macular degeneration (AMD)
3. Diabetic retinopathy
4. Glaucoma
5. Corneal disorders
6. Uveitis

Each condition offers its own set of challenges and chances for gene therapy treatments, as researchers and trials continue to study different methods to target the genetic or molecular causes.

• Vectors in Ocular Gene Therapy

The effectiveness of eye gene therapy relies greatly on the selection of vector for carrying the therapeutic genetic material. Vectors act as carriers for delivering the desired gene into specific cells, with their choice affecting how well the gene is transferred, how long it stays active, and the potential immune reaction. This part will cover the primary kinds of vectors utilized in eye gene therapy, their attributes, benefits, and restrictions.

1 Viral Vectors

Viral vectors are widely utilized in ocular gene therapy because of their high transduction efficiency and ability to offer sustained gene expression.

1.1 Adeno-Associated Virus (AAV)

- AAV has become the preferred vector for numerous ocular gene therapy uses because of its advantageous safety record and ability to effectively infect different types of retinal cells.
- **Benefits include:** - Not causing disease and unable to replicate - Prolonged gene activity - Reduced likelihood of immune response - Ability to infect both active and inactive cells - Various virus types for targeting specific cell types.
- **Restrictions:** - Restricted ability for packaging (~4.7 kb) - Possibility of pre-existing immunity in certain people.
- **Potential uses:** - LCA2 (mutations in the RPE65 gene) - Choroideremia - X-linked retinoschisis.

1.2 Lentivirus

Derived from HIV-1, lentiviral vectors have the benefit of larger packaging capacity and the capability to integrate into the host genome.

- **Benefits:** - Increased packaging capacity of about 8 kb - Gene expression remains stable due to genomic integration - Capable of transducing cells regardless of division status.
- **Constraints:** - Safety issues related to insertional mutagenesis - Narrow tropism towards photoreceptors.

- Usage: - Usher syndrome - Stargardt disease.

1.3 Adenovirus

Adenoviral vectors were one of the initial choices for ocular gene therapy, but their popularity has declined because they provoke a strong immune response.

- Benefits: - Spacious packaging ability (~36 kb) - Superior transduction effectiveness.
- Restrictions: - Powerful immune reaction - Temporary gene expression.
- Uses: - Primarily utilized in preclinical research and for conducting proof-of-concept tests.

2 Non-Viral Vectors

Non-viral vectors have safety and manufacturing benefits, but typically show lower transduction efficiencies than viral vectors.

2.1 Nanoparticles

Nanoparticles, both lipid-based and polymer-based, are being investigated as substitutes for viral vectors.

- Benefits: - Reduced chance of immune response - ability to hold a lot of genetic material - Simple production and ability to change easily.
- Restrictions: - Transduction efficiency is less than viral vectors - Gene expression duration is shorter.
- Possible uses: - Administering small interfering RNA (siRNA) - Treating eye conditions through gene therapy in the cornea.

2.2 Liposomes

Liposomes are circular structures made up of lipid layers that are capable of enclosing genetic material.

- Benefits include: - Minimal harmfulness - Can be broken down naturally - Capable of carrying extensive genetic information.
- Constraints: - Inadequate transfection efficacy - Swift elimination from the bloodstream.
- Uses: - Administering plasmid DNA or siRNA to the front part of the eye.

3. Comparison of Vector Types

When selecting a vector for ocular gene therapy, several factors must be considered:

1. Transduction efficiency: Viral vectors generally offer higher transduction efficiencies compared to non-viral vectors.
 2. Packaging capacity: The size of the therapeutic gene determines the choice of vector, with AAV having the smallest capacity and adenovirus the largest among viral vectors.
 3. Duration of gene expression: Integration-competent vectors like lentiviruses offer the potential for long-term expression, while non-integrating vectors may provide transient expression.
 4. Immunogenicity: Non-viral vectors and AAV generally elicit lower immune responses compared to adenoviral vectors.
 5. Safety profile: The risk of insertional mutagenesis with integrating vectors must be weighed against the benefits of stable gene expression.
 6. Target cell specificity: Different vectors show varying tropisms for ocular cell types, influencing their suitability for specific applications.
 7. Manufacturing and regulatory considerations: Non-viral vectors may offer advantages in terms of large-scale production and regulatory approval.
- Ultimately, the specific requirements of the therapeutic application determine the choice of vector, considering efficacy, safety, and practical factors. Continued research is being conducted to enhance current vectors and create new delivery systems in order to enhance the results of ocular gene therapy.

4. Delivery Methods

The delivery method is essential for the success of ocular gene therapy, impacting vector distribution, gene transfer efficiency, and potential adverse effects such as immune responses. This part will talk about the different techniques used in ocular gene therapy for delivering treatment, their

benefits, drawbacks, and appropriateness for specific uses.

4. Intravitreal Injection

The process of intravitreal injection entails injecting the gene therapy vector directly into the vitreous cavity of the eye.

- Benefits: - Requires minimal invasion - Suitable for outpatient procedures - Enables multiple administrations - Effective in targeting inner retinal layers and ganglion cells.
- Constraints: - Restricted entry to outer retinal layers and RPE because of internal limiting membrane barrier - Possibility of vector dispersion in the vitreous - Elevated intraocular pressure and endophthalmitis risk.
- Uses: - Gene therapy for inner retinal disorders such as diabetic retinopathy and glaucoma. Transportation of substances that inhibit blood vessel growth for diseases involving new blood vessel formation.

5 Subretinal Injection

Subretinal injection is a method of administering the vector between the photoreceptor layer and the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE).

- Benefits: - Direct entry to photoreceptors and RPE cells - Increased transduction efficacy for outer retinal layers - Specific administration with limited systemic impact.
- Downsides: - More intrusive compared to intravitreal injection - Needs specific surgical expertise - Chance of developing retinal detachment and macular hole - Typically only given once.
- Possible uses: - Gene therapy for genetic retinal diseases that impact photoreceptors or RPE such as LCA, RP, and choroideremia.

6 Suprachoroidal Delivery

Suprachoroidal administration is the delivery of the vector between the sclera and choroid.

Benefits: - Less intrusive than subretinal injection - Possibility of wider retinal coverage in contrast to subretinal injection - Lowered chance of retinal detachment.

- Restrictions: - Less clinical exposure compared to alternative methods - Chance of choroidal bleeding - Varying vector spread.
- Possible uses: - New method for administering gene therapy to the back part of the eye - Ability to treat choroidal neovascularization and uveitis.

7 Topical Application

Administering gene therapy vectors in eye drop form is referred to as topical application.

- Benefits: - Non-surgical - Easy for patients - Appropriate for multiple uses.
- Restrictions: - Restricted access to the back of the eye - Quick removal from the surface of the eye - Inefficiency in reaching retinal targets.
- Possible uses: - Gene therapy for eye conditions affecting the cornea - Opportunity for treating diseases in the front part of the eye (e.g., glaucoma).

8 Comparison of Delivery Methods

Several factors determine the selection of the delivery method.

- The position of the target cells in the eye affects the selection of the delivery method. Intravitreal injection is appropriate for targets located within the inner retina, while subretinal injection is more favorable for targets in the outer retina and RPE. Characteristics of the vector, such

as its size and physical attributes, can impact how it spreads and enters the body through various administration techniques.

- Effect duration: Certain delivery methods can accommodate multiple administrations, such as intravitreal, while others are usually restricted to just one treatment, such as subretinal.
- Safety considerations: The level of invasiveness of the procedure and potential risks should be considered, especially for inherited conditions in young individuals needing treatment.
- Immune responses: Various administration techniques can induce different levels of local and systemic immune responses, potentially affecting the treatment's effectiveness and safety.
- Feasibility of use in clinical settings may be limited by the technical intricacy of the delivery method and the requirement for specialized equipment or expertise.

- Regulatory factors: The regulatory pathway and requirements for clinical development can be influenced by the delivery method chosen. New advancements in delivery methods, like creating new injection tools and researching less invasive ways (like suprachoroidal delivery), focus on enhancing the balance between effectiveness, safety, and practicality in a clinical setting. Continuous research is actively working on enhancing current techniques and investigating novel methods to enhance the results of ocular gene therapy.

• Inflammatory and Immune Responses in Ocular Gene Therapy

Even though the eye is considered relatively immune-privileged, ocular gene therapy can provoke inflammatory and immune reactions that could affect the treatment's safety and effectiveness. Comprehending these reactions is essential for creating plans to reduce their impact and enhance treatment results. This part delves into the different elements of the immune reaction to ocular gene therapy, considering innate and adaptive immunity aspects.

1 Innate Immune Response

The initial immune response is the primary defense mechanism against foreign entities, such as gene therapy vectors and their parts. In ocular gene therapy, various components of the innate immune system play significant roles.

1.1 Role of Pattern Recognition Receptors (PRRs)

PRRs play a vital role in the innate immune system by identifying common molecular patterns linked to pathogens or cellular stress.

- Important points: - Toll-like receptors (TLRs), specifically TLR9, have the ability to detect viral DNA and induce inflammatory reactions - RIG-I-like receptors (RLRs) identify viral RNA and can stimulate the production of type I interferon - Activation of PRRs results in the generation of pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines.

1.2 Activation of Complement System

Gene therapy vectors can trigger the activation of the complement system, a group of proteins that boost the capability of antibodies and phagocytic cells to eliminate pathogens.

- Main points: - Viral vectors can activate both traditional and non-traditional ways of complement systems - The activation of complement can cause inflammation, coating of vector particles, and possible harm to tissues - Certain viral vectors, such as AAV, have developed ways to avoid being neutralized by complement system.

1.3 Involvement of Innate Immune Cells

Different types of natural immune cells are involved in the first reaction to gene therapy in the eyes.

- Macrophages in the retina, including both resident microglia and macrophages that migrate into the tissue, have the ability to engulf vector particles and release inflammatory substances. Dendritic cells function as cells that present antigens, linking innate and adaptive immune responses.

- Natural killer cells may identify and remove cells that display unfamiliar antigens.

2 Adaptive Immune Response

The immune response that is adaptive, involving both humoral and cell-mediated immunity, may take longer to develop but can significantly impact the effectiveness and safety of gene therapy in the long run.

2.1 Humoral Immunity and Antibody Production

Humoral immunity entails B cells producing antibodies that can deactivate viral vectors and transgene products.

- Main ideas: - Existing neutralizing antibodies against viral vectors (especially AAV) can lower transduction effectiveness - new antibody responses could form after gene therapy, impacting the success of future treatments -

Antibodies targeting the transgene could negate its therapeutic benefits.

2.2 Cell-Mediated Immunity

T cells have a key part in cellular immunity by detecting and getting rid of cells showing non-self-antigens.

- Main points: - CD8+ cytotoxic T lymphocytes have the ability to eliminate transduced cells that display viral or transgene antigens - CD4+ T helper cells aid in the generation of B cell antibodies and CD8+ T cell reactions - Regulatory T cells (Tregs) play a role in regulating the immune response and fostering tolerance.

2.3 Memory Responses and Implications for Repeated Treatments

The formation of immune memory could have important consequences for gene therapy in the eye, especially when thinking about the possible requirement for multiple therapies.

- Main points: - Memory B and T cells can react quickly and strongly when exposed to viral vectors or transgene products again - This response could lower the effectiveness of future treatments and raise the chance of negative immune reactions - Research is ongoing to find ways to combat memory responses, like changing vector types or using immunomodulation techniques.

3 Factors Influencing Immune Responses

Various factors can influence the magnitude and nature of immune responses to ocular gene therapy.

3.1 Vector-related Factors

- Capsid proteins: The protective protein coating of viral carriers can trigger immune reactions, with certain types provoking stronger immunity compared to others.
- Transgenic products: The therapeutic protein that is produced may be identified as foreign, particularly when the patient does not have the natural form of the protein.

- Higher levels of dosage in general are associated with more potent immune reactions.
- Vector cleanliness: Impurities from manufacturing can boost the immune response.

3.2 Host-related Factors

- Pre-existing immunity can develop from exposure to wild-type viruses or past gene therapy, leading to the production of neutralizing antibodies and memory T cells.
- Genetic background: The immune response strength and type can be influenced by host genetic factors.
- Younger people may exhibit stronger immune reactions.
- Eye health: The condition of the blood-retinal barrier and the presence of inflammation have an impact on immune privilege.

3.3 Administration-related Factors

- Method of delivery: Various administration techniques (such as intravitreal versus subretinal) can impact the nature and intensity of immune reactions.
- Surgical trauma: Invasive delivery methods can lead to local inflammation, potentially boosting immune reactions.
- Frequency of dosing: Giving multiple treatments could raise the chance of developing adaptive immune reactions.
- Strategies to Mitigate Inflammatory and Immune Responses

Dealing with the difficulties caused by inflammatory and immune reactions is essential for enhancing the safety and effectiveness of ocular gene therapy. This part looks into different tactics being created and used to reduce these reactions.

1 Vector Engineering and Optimization

Altering vector designs can decrease immunogenicity and improve transgene expression.

- Capsid manipulation: Modifying viral capsids to avoid neutralizing antibodies or improve targeting of particular cell types.
- Selection of promoters: Employing cell-specific promoters in order to restrict transgene expression to specific tissues.
- Codon optimization: Improving transgene expression and possibly decreasing potential for immune response.
- Decreasing CpG content: Lowering the amount of immunostimulatory CpG motifs in the vector genome.

2 Immunomodulation Strategies

Ways in pharmacology to reduce or change the immune system's reaction.

- Corticosteroids are frequently employed to reduce inflammation present in specific areas or throughout the body.
- Cyclosporine and tacrolimus are calcineurin inhibitors that inhibit the activation of T cells.
- Sirolimus (rapamycin): mTOR inhibitor that possesses immunosuppressive characteristics.
- Inhibitors of complement: Aiming at the complement cascade to decrease inflammation.

3 Local vs. Systemic Immunosuppression

Assessing different strategies for regulating the immune system:

- Local immune system suppression: Directly delivering immunomodulatory substances to the eye to reduce side effects in the body.
- Systemic immune suppression: Increased overall immune suppression, potentially more effective but with higher chance of side effects.
- Utilizing local and systemic treatments in combination to enhance effects synergistically.

4 Tolerance Induction Approaches

Approaches focused on promoting enduring tolerance to the vector and transgene.

- Promotion of Treg expansion to suppress undesired immune responses: Enhancing the generation of regulatory T cells.

- Antigen-specific tolerance: Administering vector elements or transgene products in a context that promotes tolerance.
- Gene therapy in newborns: Taking advantage of the developing immune system's ability to induce tolerance.

• Clinical Trials and Current Status

This part gives a summary of the present state of ocular gene therapy clinical trials and authorized treatments.

1 Successful Treatments and Approved Therapies

Vortigern (Luxturna) approved for inherited retinal dystrophy caused by RPE65 mutations. Summary of how it was developed, approved, and handled after being marketed.

2 Ongoing Clinical Trials

- Overview of current experiments for different eye-related issues (e.g., choroideremia, Xlinked retinoschisis, achromatopsia).
- Conversation about various methods being experimented with (e.g., gene substitution, genetic manipulation, optogenetics).

3 Challenges and Setbacks Related to Immune Responses

Examples of trials where immune reactions have presented major obstacles.

Insights gained from these experiences and how they have influenced following trial layouts.

4 Lessons Learned from Clinical Experiences

Significance of choosing the right patients and screening for existing immunity.

- Improving the use of vector doses and delivery techniques.
- Optimization of immunosuppression regimens.
- Considerations for long-term follow-up.

• Future Perspectives

This portion examines new developments and upcoming paths in ocular gene therapy, concentrating on tackling immune and inflammatory obstacles.

1 Novel Vector Designs and Delivery Methods

- Creating modified AAV capsids with decreased immune response.
- Investigation of non-viral vectors with enhanced safety characteristics.
- Improvements in surgical methods and tools have allowed for more accurate and less intrusive procedures.

2 Advances in Immunomodulation Strategies

- Tailored strategies to regulate particular immune pathways.
- Creation of new biologics for immune system suppression.
- Investigation of using nanoparticles to deliver agents that modulate the immune system.

3 Gene Editing and In Vivo Gene Therapy

- Applications of gene editing technologies like CRISPR-Cas9 in the field of ophthalmology.
- Challenges and potential advantages in immune reactions within gene editing strategies.

4 Combining Gene Therapy with Other Treatment Modalities

Possible advantages when combining cell therapy methods.

- Incorporation with developing drug administration techniques.
- Use of neuroprotective or anti-inflammatory therapies in combination.

CONCLUSION

Possible benefits from combining cell therapy techniques In recent years, there have been significant advancements in ocular gene therapy, providing optimism for patients with eye disorders that were previously incurable. Yet, the presence of inflammatory and immune reactions pose significant obstacles that could affect the safety and effectiveness of these therapies. This in-depth analysis has examined the complex characteristics of these reactions, from natural defense to learned responses, and the diverse factors affecting their progression. Significant advancements have been made in the field to overcome these obstacles, such

as improved vector designs, precise delivery techniques, and new immunomodulation strategies. The potential of ocular gene therapy is highlighted by the success of Luxturna and the positive outcomes of many current clinical trials. In the future, further progress in vector engineering, delivery technologies, and our knowledge of ocular immunology will be essential in addressing the remaining challenges. The combination of gene therapy with other advanced techniques like gene editing and cell therapy shows potential for improved and customized treatments. Collaboration among researchers, clinicians, and regulatory bodies will be crucial to safely and effectively translate innovative therapies from the lab to patient care as the field evolves. Continued attempts to tackle inflammatory and immune responses are leading to advancements in ocular gene therapy, which has the potential to transform the treatment of various eye disorders and provide hope for patients globally.

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